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**ADOPTION AND PREFERENCE OF DIGITAL LEARNING MODE FOR
EDUCATION AND IT'S CHALLENGES AMONG SECONDARY LEVEL STUDENTS
OF PUNE: A STUDY**

ABSTRACT:

The adaptation to digital education has brought remarkable changes to the learning experiences of secondary school students, along with numerous challenges. This study aims to understand the challenges faced by secondary school students in their educational journey and investigate their preferences for various modes of digital learning. This study uses survey methodology approach from diverse socioeconomic and educational backgrounds to explore the challenges faced by the students in adaptation of digital mode of education. The study focuses on accessibility, technological proficiency, engagement, and the effectiveness of digital tools in meeting learning objectives. The findings unveiled the critical insights into the barriers hindering students' educational progress, such as inadequate internet connectivity, limited access to devices, and a lack of personalized support. Additionally, the study highlights students' preferences for interactive and flexible digital learning modes that cater to their individual needs. The research offers valuable recommendations for policymakers, educators, and technology developers to design inclusive and effective digital education strategies, ensuring equitable learning opportunities for all secondary school students.

KEYWORDS: Digital Education, Secondary School Students, Internet Connectivity

INTRODUCTION

Education system has adopted the smart digital technologies and grown exponentially over the years, creating new possibilities to improve teaching and enhance learning. Digital technology has shown rapid change and considerable challenges throughout the modern world especially in the educational sector. National Education Policy 2020 recognizes the importance of leveraging the advantages of digital education while acknowledging its potential risks in

providing quality education for all. Education is the process of providing learning, acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, habits etc. also conveyed that the education plays a fundamental role in future growth of societies and nation economies. Education is not only restricted to textbooks and classrooms teaching but also involve the incorporation of new technologies, tools, innovative ideas, and e-content in teaching learning process. Wagner (2018) in his study unveiled the change in nature of teaching and learning process with successive development of information and communication technologies (ICTs). In India, digital education was previously seen as a material supplementary to classroom teaching (Shah and Jani, 2020). One can understand the Digital education as an incorporation of digital technology and tools in teaching and learning process. Digital education is an umbrella term for any education that could encompass the use of technology in traditional classrooms, entirely online. Digital education also covers the terminology such as Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) or digital learning or e-learning. Digital education ensures the use and sophistication of digital technologies for teaching and learning process within a community. These digital technologies need appropriate infrastructure to support such education. Digital learning is not a new concept but its significance was increased manifold after COVID-19 pandemic. Most of educational institutions are adopting digital education as solution for traditional education process of chalk and talk. Evolving technology and high-speed internet made learning interactive, engaging, motivating and handy. In near future, digital education will play prime role in learning process through the Government policies for effective implementation and adoption by educational institutions (Rani et al., 2021).

- Challenges for Online Education in India Considering need of time, NEP 2020 promotes the digital education in India. But online teaching learning has many challenges. The major challenges are as fallows
- The accessibility of high-speed internet connectivity, supporting devices, software and applications at affordable costs are prime requisites in digital education. The government needs to come forward with provision of financial support and policies that will boost the market for amenities required for the digital education in India.
- Online education needs be blended with experiential and activity-based learning otherwise it will tend to become a screen-based education and will not focus on social, emotional, physical quotient as well as overall development of student.

- Certain types of courses/subjects such as science practical and performing arts have limitations in the digital education, which needs to overcome with new and innovative measures in future.
- Teachers will require suitable training and develop themselves to become effective online educators. Teacher's familiarity for the new teaching format, platforms and tools for online education is also major challenge.
- In India, most of students are from communities like farmers, cleaners, sweepers, housemaids, waiters, etc. with financial conditions which may not support them to fulfil all the essential requirements for online education. As per the report of NSSO, only 4.4% of rural households and 23.4% of urban households own their personal computers.
- Assessment and evaluation of students in online education is a challenging task, especially in practical oriented and art-based courses.
- Survey showed that, teacher and students in the online learning process faces several challenges such as struggle for adapting to online mode, lack of focus and concentration of learners, diversion of learners to other social media platforms, health issues due to long term exposure to the screens, etc.

This paper aims to find and understand:

- the preference and adoption level of information communication technology and e-learning platform for education and its impact on the school students
- the internet accessibility and usage level of information communication technology applications for education among the secondary school students.”

Literature Review

Due to the integration of digital and internet technologies in education it plays an important role in extending the boundaries of teaching and learning. Its substantial to understand meaningful integration of digital and internet technologies so there is a need to understand their pedagogical affordances in education, and to further substantiate the arguments with practical cases. Following digitalisation in education, there have been forward thinking approaches to teaching and learning. To this effect, students must be prepared to use smart devices to improve their learning, comprehension, attentiveness, and literacy (Mhlongo et.al. 2023).

In a study it has been unveiled regarding limited availability of the ICT resources and it is required to install a greater number of systems. Further these systems usage is confined mainly to the computer labs and many times the internet connection is hardly available. So, the

availability of the ICT resources can enhance the learning of the students. This reduces the dependence of the students on the teachers and try to learn new things on their own (Lalitha, 2021).

In a study it has been found various concerns, patterns, and difficulties of computerized instruction in India and recommended the engaging ingenious homeroom approach for learning. The upcoming pattern of computerized schooling incorporates digitalized study hall, learning through videos and using playoffs for better learning, etc. she mentioned the various difficulties of computer training in India and the recommended steps to overcome this difficulty. Consistent changes needed in schools and instructor for the improvement of computerized training in India (Dua, Wadhwan, & Gupta, 2016).

Similarly, Mishra, Gupta, and Shree (2020) found that **socio-economic factors** are also very important when it comes to digital education adoption. Students coming from lower-income families face difficulties in accessing devices like laptops or tablets, leading to disparities in learning outcomes. In Pune, where urban-rural divides persist, such issues are exacerbated for secondary school students.

Moreover, a study by Singh and Thakur (2021) noted that students experience **screen fatigue and lack of engagement** in online learning. Secondary school students, who are at a formative stage of education, often struggle with motivation and attention spans during digital classes, which further hampers their academic progress.

Despite the challenges, students have shown preferences for specific digital learning tools and platforms. According to Dua et al. (2016), **interactive platforms** that include video-based learning, quizzes, and gamification are more effective in maintaining student interest and engagement. Tools like Google Classroom, Zoom, and Edmodo have been widely accepted due to their user-friendly interfaces and interactive features.

A study by Sharma and Patel (2019) revealed that students prefer **blended learning models**, which combine traditional classroom teaching with digital tools. This approach allows for greater flexibility while maintaining the benefits of face-to-face interaction. For secondary school students in Pune, this preference aligns with the need for structured learning while adapting to digital platforms.

Additionally, Kumar and Jadhav (2022) found that students are more inclined towards **mobile-based learning applications** due to their accessibility and affordability. Applications like BYJU'S, Khan Academy, and Unacademy have gained popularity among secondary school students for their personalized learning content.

METHODOLOGY

To ascertain what challenges secondary school students, face, and their choices for modes of digital learning, this study uses descriptive survey method. Considering the objectives of this study the survey method is appropriate because it allows the collection of quantitative data covering a large sample thus giving an indication of patterns, preferences and challenges students experienced. This study mainly focuses on secondary school students. The sample comprised of 560 students drawn from six different schools. The schools were purposely chosen to capture the rural and urban settings, as well as, different educational and economic backgrounds which adds on to the variability of the findings. The selection of the participants was done through purposive sampling. This non-probability sampling method was adopted to make sure that the sample consisted of students who are quite involved in the use of digital learning modes. Criteria employed included ownership of a computer, frequent use of online education sites and engaging in blended learning and total e-learning.

A structured questionnaire was designed as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire was comprised of three sections:

Demographic Information: Age, sex, class, and ownership of and access to digital devices.

Challenges Faced: Issues faced during digital education.

Preferences on Digital Modes: Questions addressing how students use different digital tools, platforms, and learning methodologies.

The questions crafted were in two formats, open ended and closed. To generate quantifiable information, closed questions were facilitated whereas open-ended questions enabled students to narrate more about themselves and their experiences and likes. The final version of the questionnaire was given out to the targeted schools. For the socio demographic students, they were given a brief explanation on the need of the research and no compulsory participation was required. The data was obtained management in both in paper form and electronically

depending on the organization of resources in that school. The gathered data was properly sorted and then statistical instruments were used to analyze it. Simple statistics in form of frequencies, percentages, averages, and standard deviations were used in presentation of the data. Thematic analysis was also used on the open-question responses to pinpoint key patterns and themes that recurred throughout the data.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

RQ 1: What is the level of Adoption of ICT For Education among students?

RQ 2: What is the level of internet accessibility?

RQ3: What are the laggings in using ICT for the educational purpose?

DATA ANALYSIS

Interpretation of the frequency tables

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	310	59.2	59.2	59.2
	Female	214	40.8	40.8	100.0
	Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.0

The data in Table 1.0 shows that out of the total 524 respondents, 310 (59.2%) are male and 214 (40.8%) are female. This indicates a higher representation of males in the sample compared to females. The cumulative percentage reveals that by adding the percentage of male respondents, 59.2% of the sample is male, and with the inclusion of female respondents, the total reaches 100%. This distribution suggests a gender imbalance, with a significantly larger proportion of males than females in the sample.

School type

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Government	128	24.4	24.4	24.4
	Private	396	75.6	75.6	100.0
	Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.1

The data in Table 1.1 shows that out of the 524 respondents, 128 (24.4%) are from government schools, while 396 (75.6%) are from private schools. This indicates a significantly higher representation of students from private schools compared to those from government schools. The cumulative percentage reveals that after accounting for the students from government schools, 24.4% of the sample is from government schools, and with the inclusion of students from private schools, the total reaches 100%. This distribution highlights a substantial majority of respondents coming from private educational institutions.

Grade

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Grade 9	247	47.1	47.1	47.1
	Grade 10	130	24.8	24.8	71.9
	Grade 11	45	8.6	8.6	80.5
	Grade 12	102	19.5	19.5	100.0
	Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.2

The data in table 1.2 reveals the distribution of students across various grades. Out of the 524 respondents, the largest group consists of Grade 9 students, making up 47.1% of the sample.

Grade 10 students account for 24.8%, while 19.5% are in Grade 12. Grade 11 students represent the smallest group, with 8.6%. The cumulative percentage shows that by including Grade 10 students, the total reaches 71.9%, and after adding Grade 11 and Grade 12 students, the full sample is represented. This indicates a strong representation of students from lower secondary grades, particularly from Grade 9.

Monthly Income of the parent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less Than 20,000	60	11.5	11.5	11.5
	20,000-30,000	55	10.5	10.5	21.9
	30,000-40,000	30	5.7	5.7	27.7
	40,000-50,000	78	14.9	14.9	42.6
	More than 50,000	301	57.4	57.4	100.0
	Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.3

The data of Table 1.3 on the monthly income of parents reveals a significant concentration of respondents in the higher income brackets, with 57.4% earning more than 50,000. A notable proportion, 14.9%, falls within the 40,000-50,000 range, while smaller segments report incomes between 20,000-30,000 (10.5%) and 30,000-40,000 (5.7%). Only 11.5% of parents earn less than 20,000, indicating that the majority of families surveyed have a relatively higher economic status. This distribution suggests that students in this sample likely come from households with considerable financial resources, which may influence their educational opportunities and access to various learning resources.

How frequently do you use Information and Communication Technology application for educational purposes?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Rarely	40	7.6	7.6	7.6
	Monthly	16	3.1	3.1	10.7
	Weekly	47	9.0	9.0	19.7
	Twice In a week	86	16.4	16.4	36.1
	Daily	335	63.9	63.9	100.0
	Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.4

The data of Table 1.4 shows how often students use Information and Communication Technology (ICT) applications for educational purposes. A significant majority, 63.9%, report using ICT daily, indicating a high level of engagement with digital tools in their learning. About 16.4% of students use ICT twice a week, while 9.0% use it weekly. A smaller portion, 7.6%, rarely use ICT, and 3.1% use it only monthly. The cumulative percentages show that most students are frequently using ICT, with 36.1% already using it at least twice a week or more, highlighting its importance in their educational activities.

How long have you been using computer and its applications for learning purposes either at school or at home?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than one year	91	17.4	17.4	17.4
	1-2 years	163	31.1	31.1	48.5
	3-5 years	136	26.0	26.0	74.4
	6-8 years	70	13.4	13.4	87.8
	More than 8 years	64	12.2	12.2	100.0
	Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.5

The data of Table 1.5 indicates how long students have been using computers and their applications for learning purposes either at school or at home. The largest group, 31.1%, has been using these technologies for 1-2 years, while 26.0% have been using them for 3-5 years. Around 17.4% of students are relatively new to ICT, with less than a year of experience. More experienced users, with 6-8 years and more than 8 years of usage, account for 13.4% and 12.2%, respectively. Overall, the data shows a mix of experience levels with technology, suggesting varying degrees of familiarity with ICT for learning, with a strong presence of students who have adopted these tools in the past 1-5 years.

How much time do you spend on any media for your educational purpose?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Less than 1 hour per day	170	32.4	32.4	32.4
1-2 hours per day	244	46.6	46.6	79.0
3-4 hours per day	74	14.1	14.1	93.1
5-6 hours per day	18	3.4	3.4	96.6
More than 6 hours per day	18	3.4	3.4	100.0
Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.6

The data of Table 1.6 illustrates the amount of time students spend on any media for educational purposes. A significant portion of students, 46.6%, spend 1-2 hours per day on educational media, which is the largest group. Another 32.4% spend less than 1 hour per day, while 14.1% dedicate 3-4 hours daily to educational media. A smaller percentage, 3.4%, spend 5-6 hours per day, and an equal 3.4% report spending more than 6 hours daily. The majority of students (79%) spend between 1 to 2 hours or less on media for educational purposes, with only a small percentage devoting more extended periods, indicating that most students engage with media moderately for educational tasks.

How much time does your school spend on all ICT facilities in the school for delivering the lecture?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Rarely	102	19.5	19.5	19.5
Occasionally	113	21.6	21.6	41.0
Less than 1 hour per day	150	28.6	28.6	69.7
1-2 hours per day	102	19.5	19.5	89.1
3-4 hours per day	57	10.9	10.9	100.0
Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.7

The data of table 1.7 shows how much time schools dedicate to using ICT facilities for delivering lectures. The largest group, 28.6%, reports that their schools use ICT facilities for less than 1 hour per day, while 21.6% mention occasional use. A similar 19.5% of respondents indicate that their schools spend 1-2 hours daily on ICT, and the same percentage says that ICT is rarely used for lectures. A smaller group, 10.9%, states that their schools use ICT for 3-4 hours per day. Overall, this suggests that while many schools use ICT regularly for lectures, there is still a significant portion where ICT usage is limited or infrequent.

What ICT resources does your school have for students to use?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Computer lab	302	57.6	57.6	57.6
Internet Facility	25	4.8	4.8	62.4

ICT enabled classroom	24	4.6	4.6	67.0
All the above	173	33.0	33.0	100.0
Total	524	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.8

The data of table 1.8 on ICT resources available to students at schools reveals that 57.6% of respondents have access to a computer lab. A much smaller portion, 4.8%, report that their schools provide an internet facility, and 4.6% mention having ICT-enabled classrooms. However, 33.0% of respondents indicate that their schools offer all of the above resources, including a computer lab, internet facility, and ICT-enabled classrooms. This suggests that while the majority of schools have computer labs, fewer schools have a comprehensive range of ICT resources available to students.

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
I encounter difficulties in accessing and utilizing online educational resources because it is complicated to learn.	524	2.9122	1.17002	.05111
The complexity of using ICT negatively impacts my motivation to engage in educational tasks.	524	2.7443	1.17310	.05125

One-Sample Test

Test Value = 3

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
I encounter difficulties in accessing and utilizing online educational resources because it is complicated to learn.	-1.718	523	.086	-.08779	-.1882	.0126
The complexity of using ICT negatively impacts my motivation to engage in educational tasks.	-4.990	523	.000	-.25573	-.3564	-.1550

Interpretation of the One-Sample Test Results:

1. I encounter difficulties in accessing and utilizing online educational resources because it is complicated to learn:

- **Test Value** = 3 (this represents the neutral point on a Likert scale where 3 suggests neither agreement nor disagreement).
- **t-value** = -1.718, **df** = 523, **p-value** = .086
- **Mean Difference** = -.08779, **95% Confidence Interval**: Lower = -0.1882, Upper = 0.0126
- **Interpretation**: The mean score for this statement (2.91) is slightly below the neutral value of 3, indicating a slight tendency toward disagreement. However, the p-value (.086) is above the 0.05 threshold, meaning that this result is **not statistically significant** at the 95% confidence level. This suggests that, on average, students do not strongly feel that the complexity of online educational resources creates substantial difficulties for them. While some students do find it challenging, the overall response leans only slightly towards this perception, and it is not a dominant issue across the sample.

2. **The complexity of using ICT negatively impacts my motivation to engage in educational tasks:**

- **t-value** = -4.990, **df** = 523, **p-value** = .000
- **Mean Difference** = -0.25573, **95% Confidence Interval**: Lower = -0.3564, Upper = -0.1550
- **Interpretation**: The mean score for this statement (2.74) is significantly below the neutral value of 3, indicating a **statistically significant** tendency toward disagreement (p-value = .000). This suggests that, for a significant portion of students, the complexity of ICT tools **does not strongly discourage their motivation** to engage in educational tasks. The negative mean difference and confidence interval further support that students generally do not find ICT complexity to be a major demotivating factor in their learning activities.

CONCLUSION

The results indicate that while some students encounter **difficulties in accessing and utilizing online educational resources** due to complexity, the issue is not widespread or strongly felt, as reflected by the non-significant p-value. The complexity of using ICT is **not perceived as a significant barrier to motivation** for engaging in educational tasks among most students. However, these findings suggest that for those who do experience challenges, it may be worth investigating further to identify specific areas of improvement, especially in simplifying the use of ICT tools.

This suggests that while there are challenges for some students, the majority do not find the complexity of ICT to be a major hindrance in their educational experience. Schools may consider offering additional support or resources to the subset of students who do face these challenges but can reasonably infer that the broad student population is generally able to adapt to the digital environment without major motivational setbacks caused by ICT complexity.

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